

BioReCer

Biological Resources Certifications Schemes

We need you!

BioReCer aims to represent the requests and needs of bio-based industry stakeholders, i.e. all members of the whole value-chain of a bio-based product. To be successful, the project relies on feedback and input from a wide range of stakeholders. Only with your participation, the project can successfully influence the transition of the EU economy to become more sustainable. Therefore, make your voice heard and become part by actively engaging in the project's "Bio Resources Stakeholder Platform" (BRSP). Here, your expertise can make a difference!

Share your perception and experience with bio-based value-chains and products, and comment on assessment methodology.

What are your opinions and views on waste as resource and derived products?

How should certification schemes be adapted to bio-based value chains?

Do you see (potential) barriers, opportunities and advantages for the bio-based economy?

And how do you see the role of policy makers?

Read more about the BRSP and become a member at biorecer.eu/brsp

What is in for you?

Bioeconomy and Industry

- Gain new business areas
- Find networking and collaboration opportunities
- Help adapt labelling and certification schemes that reflect your needs
- Increase your company's sustainability
- Provide your customers with transparent information on bio-based feedstock
- Strengthen Europe's bio-based industry and become more competitive

Certification Bodies

- Actively participate in the development of guidelines and standards for the criteria that need to be considered in bio-based certification schemes, considering regulatory, trade, environmental and social aspects.
- Help shape certification schemes for bio-based products and their value-chains

Policy Makers

- Find support for your own goals to shape the EU economy
- Gain influence on EU policy
- Support the transition towards a circular and sustainable European bioeconomy

Scientists

- Gain food for thought and learning opportunity in discussions and training actions
- Find exploitation opportunities
- Learn more about BioReCer's digital stakeholder platform (BioReCer ICT tool)

Consumers and Consumer Associations

- Gain a voice in the sustainable transition of the EU
- Find your opinion, views and needs represented
- Get easy, reliable and transparent information on the sustainability of bio-based products

Activities

Participate online or in person in Focus Groups Discussions, training capsules and brainstorming sessions related to the four different waste(water) value-chains.

Take part in workshops, training sessions and webinars.

Participate in expert groups for certification, standardisation, sustainability fields and consumer perception.

Help validate and test the BioReCer methodologies in the four different waste(water) value-chains in Spain, Italy, Greece and Sweden.

Fill in surveys and questionnaires.

Get informed in annual meetings, follow the work in progress and monitor how your input has been incorporated into the project development.

biorecer.eu

BioReCer Goals

By strengthening **certification** schemes, the BioReCer project aims to increase the acceptance of feedstock and products based on biological waste by the industry and consumers and to support the competitiveness of Europe's bio-based economy. BioReCer pursues the transition towards a circular bio-based EU economy at EU and later on global scale, in which land use is optimised and resources are not wasted. Within the BioReCer approach, the added value, the use, as well as the social acceptance of **bio-based products** will be increased. Furthermore, the project's "Bio Resources Stakeholder Platform" (BRSP) will support stakeholders in their selection of optimal alternatives to establish circular bio-based systems reversing climate change, restoring biodiversity and protecting air, soil and water quality within the EU and across borders.

Challenges

Various aspects affect the acceptance of bio-based products made from waste:

- Organic waste(water) residuals hold valuable components, such as carbon, and should not be wasted as they can substitute fossil feedstock and serve as valuable resources for bio-based products. However, waste and wastewater sludge are often discarded and incinerated or end up as landfill, which causes pollution and greenhouse gas emissions.
 - Certification schemes are often not sufficiently laid-out for bio-based products and their **value-chains**.
 - Certifications do not sufficiently reflect the environmental and sustainability benefits.
 - Biological resources vary in availability, quality and content due to environmental challenges (e.g., seasonality, weather, climate and soil conditions).
 - The current destination for most of the biological resources is a low added-value market. This is because their way through the value-chain is often not tracked and untransparent.
- This lack of traceability information continues to hinder their availability, use and profitability for the industry.
- Traceability information is not accessible for bio-based industries that are unaware of the potential of the biological resources produced in their region.
 - Bio-based products from waste are often incorrectly associated with lower quality.

Solution

The HORIZON Europe project BioReCer will assess the value-chains of bio-based products derived from waste(water) side-streams from fishery, agriculture and forestry as well as organic municipal waste(water). For this, BioReCer will develop assessment methods that are adapted for the specific characteristics of bio-based systems, e.g. by identifying and implementing suitable sustainability indicators. This will ensure reliable tracking and traceability of biological feedstock and its environmental performance. Finally, BioReCer will deploy guidelines for bio-based products to strengthen current certification schemes.

Glossary

Bio-based Product

a product that is wholly or partly derived from biomass instead of fossil feedstock. This product can be an intermediate, material, semi-finished or final product (e.g. cosmetics, pharma/ neutraceuticals, chemicals/ bioplastics, food and beverage, bio-composites, fertilizers, medical product).

Certification

is part of testing and inspection of a product and its value-chain, and the provision of written assurance (a certificate) by an independent body. This certificate confirms that the product in question and its value-chain meets specific requirements. These certificates are publicly available, and in many cases, certifiers award product labels that consumers can use as a guide for purchasing choices.

In case of bio-based products certification is challenging. This is because existing Labels and Certification Schemes (LCS) mostly use indicators and criteria that have been developed for traditional feedstocks (e.g. wood) and their applications. Also, in comparison to conventional fossil feedstock, value chains of biological resources are often long due to numerous intermediate processing steps. Consequently, more effort is required to monitor the entire supply chain and obtain transparency.

BioReCer will complement current certification schemes including new criteria for certifying the sustainability, origin and traceability of biological resources derived from waste, and ensuring applicability in the EU and globally.

Value-chain

the progression of activities that are performed by different members of the bio-based industry from production and processing of the biomass until the delivery of a final bio-based product with all intermediate steps.